
Operational Performance of Milk Producers Cooperative Society Limited in Narasingapuram, Salem District

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Abstract

Dairy cooperatives have a crucial role in strengthening the dairy sector and thereby fostering its growth and development. This study is particularly focusing on the Milk Producers Cooperative Society Limited in Narasingapuram, Salem District of Tamil Nadu. The major objectives of the study were to analyze the milk procurement, to examine the milk sales and to evaluate the profit of milk Producers Cooperative Society Limited in Narasingapuram, Salem District. The study was conducted purely based on the secondary data, which was collected mainly from the official reports of the society. Besides this various journals, websites, books etc., were also utilized. The data for the study was taken for the period from 2016 to 2025. The overall assessment of the study exhibits positive developments in the society's milk procurement over the duration of the study, particularly by union members. In addition, there was a bit encouraging trend in milk sales and profit. The data shows a small fluctuation during the period, regardless the fact that it is positive.

Therefore, it is possible to figure out that society has generally beneficial trends about the variables that have taken place.

Keywords: Dairying, Dairy Cooperatives, Milk Procurement, Milk Procurement Sales, Milk Procurement Sale Profit

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Introduction

Dairying is the process of producing various dairy products from different kinds of animals. This process has a significant role in the Indian economy. In addition to being seen from an economic perspective, dairying plays a significant role in ensuring the nation's food and nutritional security. According to India, dairying is considered as a tool of socio-economic development. The nation's milk supply comes from millions of small producers dispersed throughout the rural areas.¹ From 1946 onwards, cooperative dairying in India truly gained momentum. In order to address the exploitation of farmers by private dealers, the first farmers' integrated dairy cooperative was founded in 1946 in the Gujarati town of Anand, in the Kaira district. The common name for this cooperative is Anand Milk Union Limited or AMUL. The village level milk producers' cooperative society, a voluntary organization of milk producers who want to market their milk collectively is the fundamental unit of Anand pattern cooperatives. Every dairy cooperative society in a milk shed is a member of the district cooperative milk producers' union, which is the highest governing body. The milk union gathers milk from member dairy cooperative societies, which further processes it and sets up the sale of both liquid milk and related products. In addition to paying member dairy cooperative societies for their milk supply, the milk union provides components that boost the productivity of dairy animals.²

On 1.8.1965, the Dairy Development Department gained administrative and legal authority over all of the state's milk cooperatives. Inspired from the 'Anand Pattern', the Tamil Nadu government established the Tamil Nadu Co-operative Milk Producers' Federation Limited in the

¹ <https://www.fao.org/4/t3080t/t3080t07.htm>

² <https://www.nddb.coop/farmer/dairying/movement>

state on 01.02.1981. Thereafter, various commercial activities such as procurement of milk, processing, chilling, packing and selling etc. which was dealt by the Tamil Nadu Dairy Development Corporation Ltd. was hand over to Tamil Nadu Cooperative Milk Producers' Federation Limited, which was also known as 'Aavin'.³

The Salem District Co-operative Union Ltd. has begun its operations since 07.10.1978. This union operated across both Salem and Namakkal districts from the outset. Later on, Salem union separated into Salem and Namakkal union on 17.12.2018, for administrative purposes with Namakkal union operating as a district union. With an average of 46,782 pouring members, the Salem Union procures milk from 770 members of the Milk Producers' Cooperative Society, which has 2,29,399 members overall.⁴ Among them, this study mainly focusing on the Milk Producers Cooperative Society Limited in Narasingapuram, Salem, Tamil Nadu. This society was established in the year 1961. Currently the society is working with 11 staff and 250 members. The members are all union members. Earlier it was worked with both union and non-union members. But later on, since September 2021, the society consists of union members only. There were no non-members based on the law implemented by the Aavin institute. Thus every non-member converted as union member of the society. The study mainly focusing on analyzing the milk procurement, milk sales and profit of Milk Producers Cooperative Society Limited in Narasingapuram, Salem District.

Review of Literature

Sangameswaran R et al., (2016) evaluated the "Status of Milk Production in Salem District of Tamil Nadu: A Comparative Analysis of Milk Producers of Dairy Co-operative Society (DCS) Vis – A – Vis Private Players". Based on primary and secondary data sources, the study further discovered that small and medium-sized farmers and landless people are the majority of milk producers in the Salem district. The study additionally revealed that milk producers' milch animal output was relatively higher than that of private agency milk producers. The study has provided some recommendations that should be implemented by both private and cooperative

³ Davitha Priyadharshini A & Palani S (2023), "A Study on Consumer Satisfaction Towards Aavin Milk in Madurai District", *International Journal for Science and Advance Research in Technology*, Vol. 9, Issue. 12, pp. 195 – 199

⁴ <https://aavin.tn.gov.in/unions/-/categories/57435>

milk procurement agencies in order to enhance the standard of living for the landless and other impoverished individuals.

Sangameswaran R et.al., (2016) conducted an “Empirical Analysis of Dairy Cooperative Societies Performance in Salem District of Tamil Nadu”. The key objective of this study is to evaluate the SWOT of dairy cooperative societies in Salem district from the viewpoint of co-operative members. In order to satisfy the objective, primary data was gathered from milk producers. Based on the assessment of the study, the main benefits were the dairy development department’s solid commitment and the farmers’ custom of supplying dairy cooperative societies with milk. It was identified that dairy is a reliable source of revenue. Low milk procurement costs and inaccessibility to dairy husbandry services was observed as the main weaknesses of this sector. There are certain opportunities of providing breeding and therapeutic services in a better manner and motivating the landless farmers. The biggest risks to the societies were the intense competition from private companies for a better service delivery network and the spread of milk into distant places.

Tamila M (2019) studied the “Milk Production and Milk Marketing for Dharmapuri District in Tamil Nadu”. The study focused on the growth and development of dairy co-operative sector in Tamil Nadu and the hurdles in improving the operational efficiency of the people of the state, especially on this district. Analysis of the milk production and marketing of the milk was also discussed by the researcher. Data were collected from primary as well as secondary sources. For the analysis of the data, SPSS has been used. Tools like t-test, chi-square test, ANOVA, correlation and factor analysis were made for the detailed examination of the data. Based on the analysis made, the study had suggested for the proper training and regular updating of dairy management knowledge in order to maintain the cattle’s health, welfare and longevity, and the success of the dairy sectors.

Lawrence Seekan K and Xavior Selvakumar A (2020) conducted a detailed examination on “Performance of the Primary Agricultural Co-operative Credit Societies in Nagappattinam District of Tamil Nadu”. The goal of the study was to compile information on the performance of a few primary agricultural cooperative credit societies in Tamil Nadu's Nagapattinam region. The study was based on the various secondary sources. The study's findings showed that the chosen Primary Agricultural Co-operative Credit Societies in the research region had disappointing results across the board in terms of operational performance metrics. The fact that one society did well on one metric but poorly on another indicates that the societies' overall

operational performance has been unsatisfactory and that each society has to improve in a different area.

Sathya and Nanee (2024) conducted a study on financial performance of Aavin cooperative milk federation limited. The study was carried out in Coimbatore district of Tamil Nadu. The principal objective of this study was to investigate and forecast the ratio analysis of Aavin milk. Liquidity ratio, Solvency ratio and Profitability ratio were mainly evaluated. Primary and secondary data had been utilized for the study. The discussions of the study revealed that the company's performance must improve annually, but in order to succeed, effective management of change adaptation is required. The company's reputation and reserves are strong, which will contribute to its outstanding growth in the upcoming years.

Objectives

1. To analyze the Milk procurement of Milk Producers Cooperative Society Limited, in Narasingapuram, Salem District.
2. To examine the Milk Sales of Milk Producers Cooperative Society Limited, in Narasingapuram, Salem District.
3. To evaluate the Profit of Milk Producers Cooperative Society Limited in Narasingapuram, Salem District.

Methodology

The study has been conducted based on the secondary sources of data. The data has been collected from reports of Milk Producers Cooperative Society Limited in Narasingapuram, Salem district of Tamil Nadu, journals, websites, articles etc.

Results and Discussions

Table -1
Milk Procurement from 2016-17 to 2024-25

Sl. No.	Year	Union members			Non-members			Total		
		Sample Milk (Litres)	Milk Procurement (Litres)	Value (Rs.)	Sample Milk (Litres)	Milk Procurement (Litres)	Value (Rs.)	Sample Milk (Litres)	Milk Procurement (Litres)	Value (Rs.)
1	2016-2017	97,793	5,48,198	1,37,03,818	57,868	2,86,413	70,77,080	1,55,661	8,34,611	2,07,80,898
2	2017-2018	1,13,026	7,03,356	1,79,29,896	86,014	4,29,940	1,06,38,068	1,99,040	11,33,296	2,85,67,964
3	2018-2019	1,15,494	7,49,521	1,89,80,263	88,205	4,93,918	1,24,23,535	2,03,699	12,43,440	3,14,03,799
4	2019-2020	1,13,933	7,77,605	2,16,34,603	1,02,176	58,06,41	1,60,35,941	2,16,109	13,58,246	3,76,70,544
5	2020-2021	1,14,441	7,76,335	2,30,16,020	1,11,170	6,48,842	1,88,92,202	2,25,611	14,25,178	4,19,08,223
6	2021-2022	1,84,219	11,98,554	3,54,65,381	34,038	2,05,559	60,39,885	2,18,257	14,04,114	4,15,05,267
7	2022-2023	2,09,121	14,90,468	4,58,71,408	0	0	0	2,09,121	14,90,468	4,58,71,408
8	2023-2024	1,81,570	12,54,482	4,06,04,141	0	0	0	1,81,570	12,54,482	4,06,04,141
9	2024-2025	1,79,695	12,89,695	4,18,69,857	0	0	0	1,79,695	12,89,695	4,18,69,857
Total		13,09,292	87,88,214	25,90,75,387	4,79,471	20,64,672	7,11,06,711	17,88,763	1,14,33,530	29,62,72,101
Mean		14,5,477	9,76,468	2,87,86,154	53,275	1,70,880	79,00,746	1,98,751	12,70,392	3,29,19,122
CGR %		6.99	9.97	13.21	-0.08	-0.05	-0.03	1.61	4.95	8.09

Source: Milk Producers Co-operative Society Limited in Narasingapuram, Salem District.

Figure -1
Sample Milk Procurement from 2016-2017 to 2024-2025

Figure – 2
Milk Procurement from 2016- 2017 to 2024-2025

Figure -3
Milk Procurement from 2016- 2017 to 2024- 2025 (Value in Rs.)

Table -1 was presents the informations of milk procurement from the financial years 2016-2017 to 2024-2025 in detail. Sample milk, quantity of milk procures from Union members and Non-members and the value of milk. In Milk producers Cooperative Society Limited Narasingapuram in Salem District. The society is collecting 60 ml of milk as sample milk from each member in both morning and evening. The society has an overall members of 264. This quantity is shown in the table under the category of sample milk. Furthermore, mean and compound growth rate of sample milk, quantity of milk procured and value of milk was also given in the above table. Since 2022, the society consists of union members only. Now there are no non-members based on the law implemented by the Aavin institute. Thus every non-member converted as union member of the society.

The above table and figures consists of the informations about the milk procurement from the period 2016-2017 to 2024 -2025. The data give a picture that in 2016-2017 period, sample milk procured of milk by union members was only 97,793 litres which was later increased to 1,79,695 litres in the year 2024-2025. The union members over the entire period achieved a sample milk of 13,09,292 litres in total with an average value of Rs.1,45,477 at the growth rate of 6.99%. In contrast to this, the contribution made by the non-members was comparatively less than the union members' contributions. The sample milk procurement by non-members was 57,868 litres in the year 2016-2017 which was later come down to 34,038 litres in the year 2021-2022. The part of non-members in regard to the sample milk procured. Thus for the all years of the study, non-members have a negative growth rate of -100%, with a mean value of Rs.53,275. In respect to the litres of milk procured by the union members, it was showing that 9.97% of growth rate was occurred during the period from 2016-2017 to 2024-2025, with an overall contribution of 87,88,214 litres from the part of union members alone. In regard to the litres of milk procured from the non-members, they have contributed a sum of 20,64,672 litres over the period with a growth rate of -0.05%. From 2022-2023 they were merged in contributions. Same in matter to the value of milk procured too, union members were played a major role than the non-members. A total of Rs.25,90,75,387 was made by the union members whereas the share of non-members was Rs.7,11,06,711. The union members stood at the compound growth rate of 13.21% whereas the non-members at -0.03%. The analysis of the data states that union members' contributions have a cyclical trend. And the non-members' contributions clearly showing a downward trend over the period of the study. The downward movement of contribution of non-members was mainly due to the abolishment of the category of the non-members from the society from 2021.

Table - 2
Milk Sales from 2016-17 to 2024-25

Sl. No	Year	Local Sales (Litres)	Value (Rs.)	Sales to Aavin (Litres)	Value (Rs.)	Total Sales (Litres)	Value (Rs.)
1.	2016-17	70,589	24,70,758	9,61,833	2,64,89,786	10,32,422	2,89,60,244
2.	2017-18	85,601	29,96,214	10,46,565	2,86,16,044	11,32,166	3,16,22,258
3.	2018-19	57,919	20,27,324	11,90,596	3,29,85,106	11,49,495	3,50,12,430
4.	2019-20	50,972	19,33,574	13,08,443	3,94,81,873	13,59,415	4,14,15,447
5.	2020-21	62,516	25,00,820	13,65,041	4,32,96,192	14,27,557	4,57,97,012
6.	2021-22	80,992	30,37,296	13,28,192	4,21,49,584	14,09,184	4,46,38,876
7.	2022-23	1,01,464	38,96,291	13,92,400	4,55,09,797	14,93,864	4,94,06,088
8.	2023-24	1,26,295	51,92,290	11,30,567	3,89,95,060	13,54,913	4,78,69,629
9.	2024-25	96,568	43,45,876	11,95,829	4,12,06,503	14,00,096	4,93,48,411
	Total	7,32,916	2,84,00,443	1,09,19,466	33,87,29,945	1,17,59,113	37,40,70,395
	Mean	81,435	31,55,605	12,13,274	3,76,36,661	13,06,568	4,15,63,377
	CGR %	3.54	6.48	2.45	5.03	3.44	6.10

Source: Milk Producers Co-operative Society Limited in Narasingapuram, Salem District.

Table-2 presents the yearly performance data from 2016-17 to 2024-25 for Local sales, Sales to Aavin and Total sales in litres segments value. The Local sales segment shows a mean value of 81,435 litres and a total value of Rs.2,84,00,443. The Compound Growth Rate (CGR) is 3.54% for litres and 6.48% for value, indicating a moderate positive trend. The data reveal fluctuations, with drops sharply in 2018-19, 57,919 litres and spikes in 2022-23, 1,01,464 litres. The Aavin sales segment had a mean value of 12,13,274 litres and a total value of Rs.3,33,87.29,945. Its Compound Growth Rate is 2.45% for value rise steadily from 9,61,833 litres in 2016-17 to 13,92,400 litres in 2022-23, then jump to 11,95,829 litres in 2024-25. The Total column aggregates both segments, with a mean of 13,06,568 litres and a total value of Rs.37,40,70,395. The overall Compound Growth Rate is 3.44% for litres and 6% for value. Total climbs from 10,32,422 litres in 2016-17 to 14,00,996 litres in 2024-25, with value rising from Rs.2,89,60,244 to Rs.4,93,48,411, market growth over the period.

Table - 3**Profit from 2016-2017 to 2024-2025**

Sl.No	Year	Profit (Rs.)
1.	2016-17	22,79,347
2.	2017-18	30,60,736
3.	2018-19	36,09,036
4.	2019-20	37,44,904
5.	2020-21	38,88,788
6.	2021-22	36,77,618
7.	2022-23	35,34,686
8.	2023-24	35,83,201
9.	2024-25	36,82,526
	Total	3,10,60,842
	Mean	34,51,205
	CGR	5.47%

Source: Milk Producers Co-operative Society Limited in Narasingapuram, Salem District.

Figure - 3**Profit from 2016-2017 to 2024-2025**

The profit by year from 2016-17 to 2024-25 is shown in the above table and figure. The table offers a long-term view of milk procurement operations profitability trends over nine years. The result shows that the annual profits varied significantly over the course of the study with the profit of ₹22.79 lakh in the year 2016-2017 and with the profit of ₹30.61 lakh in 2017-2018. Profits then gradually recovered and stabilized during 2018-19 and 2020-21, ranging from ₹36.09 lakh to ₹38.89 lakh (which is the most profit financial year of the study period). Profits fell to ₹36.78 lakh in 2021-2022 and then to ₹35.35 lakh in 2022-2023, it is indicating a slight decrease trend starting in 2021-2022. Profits in 2024-2025 once more showed stagnation, despite a minor improvement in 2023-2024. Over the whole period, the average yearly profit was Rs.34.51 lakh. A general upward movement of the profitability during the study period is indicated by the compound growth rate of 5.47%. The positive compound growth rate indicates profitability despite times of partial recovery and short-term stability, highlighting the necessity of strategic actions to improve financial performance and guarantee the sustainability of milk procurement operations.

Conclusion

Dairying plays an important role in the growth of the economy. For this dairy cooperative sector also plays a crucial role. From the bottom of the society to the global level, from members and staff of the society to the wide ranging consumers, it is expanded and grown more. The study mainly focuses on the Milk Producers Cooperative Society Limited in Narasingapuram, Salem District. It is located in Attur in Salem district of Tamil Nadu. The overall analysis of the study reveals a positive trend in the milk procurement of the society, especially by the union members throughout the period of the study. Besides this, sales milk procurement and milk procurement sale profit also showed a moderate positive trend. Even though it is positive, the data reveals some fluctuations during the period. Thus it could be understanding that the society has an overall positive trends on the factors which have taken. It is a great contributor to the growth of milk sector of the state. However, the constant monitoring by the authorities as well as the government and both more financial and advanced technical support could help the sector for its further growth and development.

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